

STRAIN MONITORING TECHNIQUE FOR BONDED JOINTS BY FIBRE-OPTIC DISTRIBUTED SENSORS

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SUMMARY

We applied the novel fibre-optic sensor which can measure the strain distribution along fibre Bragg gratings with the high spatial resolution to strain sensing of a single lap joint. A fibre Bragg grating whose length was about 100 mm was embedded into the adhesive of the joint and we could successfully measure the strain distributions.

Keywords: Bonded joint, Fibre-optic sensor, Strain monitoring, Fibre Bragg Grating, OFDR

INTRODUCTION

The use of adhesive bonding in composites is recently increasing because it has advantages over mechanically fastened joints, such as less sources of stress concentrations, more uniform distribution of load and better fatigue properties. In addition, cost and weight savings can be caused by it. However, the adhesive bonded joints often vary in quality depending on the skill or experience of manufacturers. Therefore, understanding the behavior of the adhesive joint is required for improving the reliability of a structure with bonding joints.

Analytical and numerical approaches to determine stress or strain distributions inside the adhesive and at the interfaces between the adhesive and the adherents have been proposed by many researchers [1, 2, 3]. On the other hand, although strain of the surface on the adherents could be measured and compared with analytical results, it is difficult to measure strain inside the adhesive and at the interfaces by conventional sensors, such as strain gauge.

As advanced sensing technologies, fibre-optic sensors which can be embedded inside the adhesive joints are attractive tools for providing a solution for this problem. Additionally, they have a feature to implement not only point sensing but also distributed sensing, so that they may measure the variation of the strain distribution inside the adhesive. Fibre-optic distributed sensor using Brillouin scattering has been recognized as a promising one for structural health monitoring (SHM). Fiber-optic sensor based on Brillouin optical time domain reflectometry (BOTDR) [4] and Brillouin optical correlation domain analysis (BOCDA) [5] can measure strain at an arbitrary position along an optical fibre. Although the spatial resolution of the former was 1 m, it

has been improved up to several cm by BOCDA. However, the spatial resolution of several cm may be not enough to comprehend the strain distribution in the adhesive joint because stress of the adherent can be transferred to the adhesive in the shorter distance.

Recently, we have developed a distributed strain measurement system using long gauge Fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors based on optical frequency domain reflectometry (OFDR) system [6]. It can measure a strain distribution with the high spatial resolution of less than 1 mm at an arbitrary position along the FBG. So it enables us to measure locally fluctuating strain distribution precisely.

In this study, we embedded the long gauge FBG sensors whose gauge length was about 100 mm inside the adhesive of a single-lap joint. We could successfully measure the strain distribution at the interface between the adhesive and the adherent during the manufacturing process. The residual strain could be also observed. Then, the strain distributions of the single-lap joint subjected to the tensile loads were measured. In this test, we could detect the degradation and damage of the adhesive joint. Consequently, we could confirm that the fibre-optic distributed strain sensing technique is useful for health monitoring and understanding the behavior of the adhesive joints.

PRINCIPLE OF DISTRIBUTED STRAIN SENSING

In this section, we explain the principle of FBG sensor and the sensing system with OFDR which can enable us to map a strain profile, namely measure a strain distribution, along the FBG sensor. Also we show a measurement result by using this distributed sensing technique.

FBG Sensor

FBG is an intrinsic device with periodic perturbation of refractive index in the core of an optical fibre [7]. When spectrally broadband light is injected into the fibre with FBG, narrowband spectral component at a specified wavelength, called Bragg wavelength is reflected as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 FBG Sensor.

So FBG is usually used as a filter device in the fibre-optic communication system. The Bragg wavelength λ_B is given by

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{eff}\Lambda, \quad (1)$$

where Λ is the pitch of the grating, and n_{eff} is the effective index of refraction of the core. When the pitch of FBG is mechanically changed by the applied strain, we can observe the wavelength shift in the reflected spectrum proportional to the change of the pitch. Therefore we can use FBG as a strain sensor, and strain of a structural member or inside a composite can be measured by monitoring the reflected light of FBG bonded on the surface or embedded into the laminate.

Sensing System with OFDR

The sensing system of this study consists of a wavelength tunable laser, photodiode detectors (D1, D2), broadband reflectors (R1, R2, R3), 3 dB couplers (C1, C2, C3), a long gauge FBG whose gauge length is about 100 mm and a computer with an A/D converter. The arrangement of the system is shown in Fig. 2. This arrangement is similar to that of Ref. [8] except using the long gauge FBG. When an incident light swept for a prescribed span of wavelength is injected into the system, the light is split by the couplers and reflected by the reflectors and the FBG. Then the interference signals of the reflected lights are detected by the detectors. An interference signal D_1 observed by the photodiode D1 is given by

$$D_1 = 2\{1 + \cos(2n_{eff}L_R k)\}, \quad (2)$$

where L_R is the path difference between the reflector R1 and the reflector R2 and k is the wavenumber of the incident light given as $k=2\pi/\lambda$. As laser tuned, the light intensity observed by D1 varies in a cycle depending on a wavenumber change $\Delta k = \pi/n_{eff}L_R$. By using this signal as an external clock for A/D converter, we can sample the signal of D2 with the constant wavenumber interval, Δk . The signal D_2 is given by

$$D_2 \approx \sum_i R_i(k)\cos(2nL_i k), \quad (3)$$

where $R_i(k)$ is the spectrum reflected by i -th grating in the FBG, L_i is a path difference between reflector R3 and the i -th grating. Thus the signal D_2 is represented as the summation of interference signals of reflected lights from the reflector R3 and from each grating in the FBG.

The waveform of signal D_2 obtained from a FBG with the gauge length of 100 mm for uniform strain is shown in Fig. 3. The signal D_2 is depending on the intensity of the

reflected light including oscillating components with frequencies corresponding to the path difference L_i . Then by applying Fourier transform analysis with a sliding window to the signal, we can separate the reflected spectra from each grating in the FBG as a spectrogram as shown in Fig. 4. The horizontal axis represents wavelength of spectra, the vertical represents position and the color contrast represents the power of the spectra. In this spectrogram, we can see uniform reflection spectra along the FBG (1.00 m to 1.10 m). By determining the center wavelength of the spectra at each position in the spectrogram, we can map the strain profile along the long gauge FBG. In this study, we determined the center wavelength by calculating the center of the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of spectrum at each position in the spectrogram.

Figure 2 Sensing system with OFDR.

Figure 3 Waveform of signal D_2 .

Figure 4 Spectrogram.

Distributed Strain Measurement

We verified the spatial resolution of the measurement system by measuring the strain distribution adjacent to holes in an aluminum tensile specimen [9]. The specimen had one hole with the diameter of 4 mm and two holes with the diameter of 2 mm as shown in Fig. 5. The holes were located serially in the load direction and a 100 mm FBG sensor was bonded on the specimen along the holes. In Fig. 6, the strain distributions calculated by finite element method (FEM) and the measurement simulator developed by our laboratory are shown as well as that measured by the measurement system is. The tensile load was about 3 kN and the mesh size in FEM is about 0.25 mm. The

response distance, namely the spatial resolution, of the simulator in this case is 0.62 mm. The agreement between strain distributions simulated and measured is excellent, thus it can be said that the measurement system have the high spatial resolution of about 0.6 mm.

Figure 5 Specimen with holes and FBG sensor.

Figure 6 Strain distributions along the FBG sensor adjacent to the holes.

DISTRIBUTED STRAIN SENSING OF BONDED JOINT

In this study, we embedded an FBG sensor inside the adhesive of a single-lap joint and measure the strain distribution during the cure process and the static tensile tests. The specimen used and the measurement results in the cure process monitoring and in the tensile tests are shown below.

Specimen and Sensor Arrangement

Dimensions of the test specimen and the location of the FBG sensor are shown in Fig.7. The specimen is a single-lap joint of two aluminum plates (Aluminum Alloy 2017)

adhered by epoxy adhesive (Araldite 2011). Overlap length and thickness of the adhesive layer are 30 mm and 1 mm, respectively. The long gauge FBG sensor whose gauge length and diameter were 90 mm and about 150 μm , respectively, was set on the V-shaped groove machined on the aluminum plate and bonded by the same epoxy as the adhesive. The grating of the region A (40 mm) was bonded on the left adherent to measure the strain distribution of the left adherent which was outside the adhered section. The region B (30 mm) was embedded inside the adhered section of the joint to measure strain distribution at the interface between the adhesive and the adherent. The region C (20 mm) was kept free to be used as reference part for compensation.

Figure 7 Dimensions of specimen and location of FBG sensor.

Strain Measurements in Cure Process

The specimen was made as the following processes. First, FBG sensor was set on the V-shaped groove machined on one adherent of an aluminum plate and bonded using the epoxy adhesive. Then two adherents were bonded using the same adhesive so as to form a single-lap joint. The adhesive was cured as clamping the joint with vise and leaving it at the room temperature for a day. After curing at room temperature, the adhesive was post-cured at 40 °C for 16 hours.

Since stress state of the joint was possibly changed through the manufacturing processes, we monitored the strain distribution along the FBG sensor at each process.

Figure 8 shows the results of the curing process monitoring. There are two strain distributions, one is that before the adhesive is post-cured and just after bonding the FBG sensor, and another is that after post-cured. These strain distributions were determined by subtract the initial center wavelength distribution measured before bonding the FBG sensor onto the adherent from those before and after post-cure, respectively. These center wavelengths were determined from the spectrograms as shown in Fig. 9. As shown in Fig. 8, the strain distribution inside the adhesive layer, namely the region B, drastically changed as a result of the post-curing process. The residual strain ranged from about -100 $\mu\epsilon$ to about -700 $\mu\epsilon$, and the distribution profile of the residual strain was not uniform.

Figure 8 Strain distributions before and after post-cure.

Figure 9 Spectrograms before bonding and after post-cure.

Tensile Tests

The specimen was subjected to static tensile loads and the strain distributions along the FBG were measured. The load cases in the tensile tests are shown in Fig. 10. During the case #7 the single-lap joint was broken at the load of 3920 N as debonding. The measured strain distributions of the case #4 and #7 are shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, respectively.

In the case #4, as shown in Fig. 11, the agreement of strain distributions between loading and unloading is excellent. In the region A, we can see a large deformation in the lower load as the specimen was bended, and then almost linearly deformed. In the region B, it is observed that stress concentrates around the boundary between the region A and B. After unloaded, we observed a small residual strain not only around the boundaries between A and B but also between B and C. These boundaries are also the edges of the adhesive. The residual strain might be caused by some plastic deformation in the adhesive or the adherent or by some damage between the adhesive and the adherent.

In the case #7, distribution profile around the boundary between A and B differs from the case #4. It seems that the condition of stress transferring changed between case #4 and #7 due to some defect. Thus the degradation or damage is considered to occur in the adhesive as a result of large peel force at the edge of the adhered region.

Figure 13 shows the strain distributions around the boundary between the region A and B at the load of 1180 N in each load cases. The left graph shows the strain distributions when loading, and the right is when unloading. As can be seen from the figure, the profile of the strain distribution drastically changed when unloading in the case #5. The strain distribution was redistributed and developed into the inside of the adhesive. This profile of the strain distribution was maintained in the following cases. It can be said that the degradation or damage of the adhesive layer was occurred in the unloading process of the case #5.

Figure 10 Load cases in the static tensile test.

Figure 11 Strain distributions under the static tensile loads (case #4).

Figure 12 Strain distributions under the static tensile loads (case #7).

Figure 13 Strain distributions around the joint edge (left: loading, right: unloading).

CONCLUSIONS

We developed the distributed strain sensing system based on OFDR that can measure the strain distribution along the long gauge FBG with the high spatial resolution. In this paper, we applied this fibre-optic sensor system to monitoring the strain distributions inside the single-lap adhesive joint, using the embedded FBG at the interface between the adhesive and the adherent. We could successfully embed the long gauge FBG inside the adhesive joint and monitor the strain profile during the manufacturing processes. The residual strain could be observed. Then by subjecting the single-lap joint to the static tensile loads, we could detect the change of strain distribution due to the degradation or damage of the adhesive joint. Consequently we could confirm that the fibre-optic distributed strain sensing system is useful for structural health monitoring and understanding the behavior of the adhesive joints. In the near future, we can show the result of the comparison between the measured distribution and the calculated one by FEM model without damage and with damage.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We wish to acknowledge Mr. Keiji Fujibayashi of the University of Tokyo for supports of an experiment and Mr. Koji Omichi of Fujikura Ltd. for his advises to design the FBG sensor.

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